

A P O L L O

D6.5: 1st Intermediate Evaluation Report

WP6 – Pilot operation and evaluation

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Executive summary

The deliverable at hand – the 1st Intermediate Evaluation Report – provides an overview of the evaluation activities in terms of user acceptance that carried out in the course of the APOLLO project at the locations of the three pilot areas and presents results and findings. The 1st Intermediate Evaluation Report consists of four chapters:

- In the first chapter, the reasoning for conducting a survey to alpha users based on questionnaires is presented. Also, a literature review on the importance of questionnaire surveys for evaluating different products and services is presented. Moreover, there is reference on the people that participated in the survey as well as at the areas that the survey took place.
- In the second chapter, the questionnaire results are presented in terms of section and alpha users group. Also, the results are analysed in order to identify the usability, acceptance and reliability of the APOLLO services and platform for each group of the alpha users.
- The third chapter contains information on the work that will follow from this stage of the project and after in order to evaluate the APOLLO platform and services. This work will help having quantitative results as well as widening the impact of APOLLO project by involving more users in the project.
- The fourth and final chapter contains the conclusions that were derived from this questionnaire survey and on the way that they will help in the development of the APOLLO services and platform evaluation.

1 Introduction

The main objective of the APOLLO project is to develop a commercial platform that will provide advisory services to small farmers regarding i) tillage scheduling, ii) irrigation scheduling, iii) crop growth monitoring and iv) crop yield estimation. The services are based on Earth Observation Data coming from the EU's Sentinel satellites as well as on free online databases. These data are inserted in state-of-the-art algorithms for providing valuable information to small farmers and crop consultants regarding the aforementioned services.

The commercial success of APOLLO project depends highly from its users' acceptance. User acceptance is based on instances of good usability experience, accessibility, reliability and the degree of satisfaction. Questionnaire survey is considered a fundamental way for evaluating products and services.

When needs and expectations of customer of products and services are satisfied over their duration, we can speak about the customer satisfaction. The level of customer satisfaction is assessment of how the customer understands the business activities of logistics companies as their supplier. Customers are satisfied with services when their expectations are confirmed. Otherwise, the customers are dissatisfied. The expectations of customers are based on their experiences with the level of provided products and services (Stopka et al., 2016). The quality evaluation and measurement represents a tool for objectification and quantification of quality level of provided products and services (Simkova and Konecny, 2013). Moreover, stakeholder surveys are a questionnaire-based quantitative tool, most often used by projects or organisations to increase their understanding of the knowledge, attitudes, perceptions, interests and experiences of their stakeholders –both internal and external. Findings are used to make improvements in the delivery of products and/or services. Stakeholder surveys differ from other monitoring and evaluation tools in that they are not restricted to the direct clients/users of a given product and/or service, but also include a wide range of individuals and organizations that have a variety of stakes in the organization's products and services. Stakeholder surveys can be very helpful in generating critical information required for performance management and for creating and sustaining organizational change (Sadashiva, n.d.). Many have used this type of questionnaire surveys for assessing perceptions and attitudes regarding provided products and services. For instance Lee and Yom (2007) used a questionnaire survey to assess the quality of nursing services. Aerni (2002) identified the stakeholder attitudes toward the risks and benefits of agricultural biotechnology in developing countries. Kontogianni et al. (2001) evaluated the environmental assets of an island. Austin et al. (2015) evaluated the stakeholder perceptions of the effectiveness and efficiency of agri-environment schemes in enhancing pollinators on farmland. While Verner et al. (2005) proved the usability of questionnaire surveys on software project success. Carletto et al. (2010) used a questionnaire survey for improving the availability, quality and policy-relevance of agricultural data. Karetsos et al. (2007) used questionnaires for evaluating an online multilingual organic agriculture e-services platform.

Based on the aforementioned it was important for the APOLLO project to assess the APOLLO services user experience by conducting a questionnaire survey at this phase of the project. This document -the 1st Intermediate Evaluation Report of APOLLO project- presents the results from this questionnaire survey. The survey was conducted at the pilot areas (Pella region – Greece, Ruma region – Serbia, Castilla La-Mancha – Spain). The people who participated in this survey were the alpha users of the APOLLO project as they were selected during the Task 2.3 – Co-creation of Services process. The alpha users consist of three (3) farmers and one (1) crop consultant from each pilot area and helped in the development of the APOLLO services and platform by testing them at different phases. The alpha users followed the guidelines that were provided to them by the

UBFCE team (WP6 leader), while the survey was conducted by the shadows who were also selected for the co-creation process. The questionnaire is divided in seven sections. Specifically, the first section requests information on demographic characteristics, the second section requests general information on type of crops and cultivated areas that they used APOLLO platform, the third, fourth, fifth, sixth and seventh sections have questions on APOLLO tillage scheduling service, on APOLLO irrigation scheduling service, on APOLLO crop growth monitoring service, on APOLLO crop yield estimation service and on APOLLO platform accordingly. More on the guidelines that were used for the questionnaire survey can be found in ANNEX I, while the questionnaires that were used for farmers and crop consultants can be found on Annex II and Annex III accordingly.

2 APOLLO Platform Services User Experience

The questionnaire results are presented in this chapter according to the each section of the questionnaire survey and in comparison with the answers that were given by the two different alpha users groups of the APOLLO platform and services namely the farmers and the crop consultants.

2.1 Demographics

The farmers were mostly of young age (44.4% were between 18-34 years) while 67% of the crop consultants were between 35-44 years old. Most participants were males except of one woman who was participating as a crop consultant at the Spanish pilot area. Regarding the education level of the farmers 55.6 % had a bachelor degree while 33.3% had secondary education and one had a post graduate degree. Only one crop consultant had a post graduate degree while the others had a bachelor degree in Agronomy. The results can be seen in [Table 1](#).

Table 1 – Questionnaire results on demographics

2.2 General Information

Most farmers used APOLLO services on arable crops like on cotton, wheat, maize, soya, barley, sunflower except of one Spanish farmer that used APOLLO services on almonds. Accordingly, the two crop consultants in Greece and Serbia were using the APOLLO services on arable crops except of the Spanish crop consultant. Most of the farmers (55.5%) used APOLLO platform services for farms up to 30 ha while all three crop consultants used them on fields covering an area between 100 ha and 300 ha.

2.3 Tillage Scheduling Service

Most of farmers and crop consultants stated that the APOLLO tillage scheduling service helped them to organize their tillage operations while their tillage operations were more effective compared to their current practices. Additionally, a large percent of farmers and crop consultants stated that they found useful APOLLO's tillage scheduling service (77.8% and 66.7% accordingly). According to the results of the questionnaire the farmers and crop consultants answered that the service helps on the decrease on their/ their clients' fuel consumption for tillage operations. Based on the aforementioned, most farmers (71.4%) stated that are somewhat satisfied on the performance of APOLLO's tillage scheduling service while the crop consultants stated that they were neither unsatisfied nor satisfied (50%) and satisfied (50%). Both farmers and crop consultants considered that the APOLLO tillage scheduling service gives a good value on their operation. Regarding the frequency of use of the APOLLO tillage scheduling service most farmers stated that they used it up to three times a year (66.6%) compared to most crop consultants who used it in a weekly basis (66.7%). Both farmers and crop consultants agreed that the APOLLO tillage scheduling service provided somewhat satisfactory quality of information (77.8% and 66.7% accordingly). While most farmers (66.7%) stated that they had accurate information on tillage which contradicted the answers that most crop consultants gave (66.7% stated that received somewhat accurate information from the tillage scheduling service). All crop consultants found it easy to learn using APOLLO tillage scheduling service while the farmers answered in many ways (11.1% found the service somewhat difficult to learn, 33.3% found it not difficult to learn it. and 55.6% found it very easy to learn it). The 55.4% of the farmers stated that the tillage scheduling service was somewhat practical, while 50% of the crop consultants answered the same compared to the other 50% of the crop consultants who stated that tillage scheduling was practical and helped their clients solve their tasks without additional effort. Both groups agree that the tillage scheduling service provides predictable results (88.9% of the farmers and 100% of the crop consultants) and thus they feel that they are in control when using this service. This was based on their experience with soil tillage operations. In addition, both groups

found interesting to use this service and most of them like using it (55.6% of the farmers and 66.7% of the crop consultants). Regarding their perception on the performance of APOLLO tillage scheduling method compared to other methods, most crop consultants answered that it provided the same results (66.7%) while the answers of farmers varied significantly with most of them (37.5%) answering that it was better method compared to their current practices. Finally, both groups stated that they will purchase the APOLLO tillage scheduling service for using it next season and probably or definitely will suggest this to their friends (88.8% of the farmers and 100% of the crop consultants). The questionnaire results on APOLLO's tillage scheduling service can be seen in [Table 2](#).

Table 2 – Questionnaire results on APOLLO's tillage scheduling service

Tillage Scheduling Service													
Farmers	Crop Consultants												
<table border="1"> <tr><td>No</td><td>22.2%</td></tr> <tr><td>Yes</td><td>77.8%</td></tr> </table>	No	22.2%	Yes	77.8%	<table border="1"> <tr><td>No</td><td>33.3%</td></tr> <tr><td>Yes</td><td>66.7%</td></tr> </table>	No	33.3%	Yes	66.7%				
No	22.2%												
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Yes	66.7%												
Q10 Did the Tillage Scheduling Service help you to better organize your / your clients' tillage operations?													
<table border="1"> <tr><td>No</td><td>22.2%</td></tr> <tr><td>Yes</td><td>77.8%</td></tr> </table>	No	22.2%	Yes	77.8%	<table border="1"> <tr><td>No</td><td>33.3%</td></tr> <tr><td>Yes</td><td>66.7%</td></tr> </table>	No	33.3%	Yes	66.7%				
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Yes	77.8%												
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Yes	66.7%												
Q11 Was the tillage operation using APOLLO advice more effective than the reference one?													
<table border="1"> <tr><td>Very Useful</td><td>22.2%</td></tr> <tr><td>Useful</td><td>77.8%</td></tr> <tr><td>Not Useful</td><td>0%</td></tr> </table>	Very Useful	22.2%	Useful	77.8%	Not Useful	0%	<table border="1"> <tr><td>Very Useful</td><td>33.3%</td></tr> <tr><td>Useful</td><td>66.7%</td></tr> <tr><td>Not Useful</td><td>0%</td></tr> </table>	Very Useful	33.3%	Useful	66.7%	Not Useful	0%
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Q12 Do you find tillage scheduling service useful?													

Tillage Scheduling Service																									
Farmers	Crop Consultants																								
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No	20%																								
Yes	80%																								
Response	Percentage																								
No	0%																								
Yes	100%																								
<p>Q13 Was the tillage operation using APOLLO advice more effective than how you tillage / advice for tillage without APOLLO?</p>																									
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<p>Q14 Did the Tillage Scheduling Service help you/ your clients to decrease your / your clients' fuel consumption on tillage operations?</p>																									
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<p>Q15 Are you satisfied with the way APOLLO tillage scheduling service performed?</p>																									
<table border="1"> <tr><th>Response</th><th>Percentage</th></tr> <tr><td>An exceptional value</td><td>10%</td></tr> <tr><td>A good value</td><td>85%</td></tr> <tr><td>A poor value</td><td>5%</td></tr> </table>	Response	Percentage	An exceptional value	10%	A good value	85%	A poor value	5%	<table border="1"> <tr><th>Response</th><th>Percentage</th></tr> <tr><td>An exceptional value</td><td>0%</td></tr> <tr><td>A good value</td><td>100%</td></tr> <tr><td>A poor value</td><td>0%</td></tr> </table>	Response	Percentage	An exceptional value	0%	A good value	100%	A poor value	0%								
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<p>Q16 Considering the overall value of the tillage scheduling service, was it...</p>																									

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Farmers	Crop Consultants																																
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Q17 How often did you typically use the tillage scheduling service?																																	
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Q18 What is your impression on the overall quality of the information provided by the tillage scheduling service?																																	
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Q19 How accurate did you find the information provided by the service?																																	
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Q20 How easy was it to learn using this APOLLO service?																																	

2.4 Irrigation Scheduling Service

All farmers and crop consultants not only agreed that APOLLO’s irrigation scheduling service helped them to better organize irrigation operations, but it was also more effective than the current methods they use to schedule irrigation. Moreover, both groups found this service useful and very useful. Most of farmers and crop consultants answered that APOLLO’s irrigation scheduling service helped them decrease water consumption for irrigation (87.5% and 66.7% accordingly). In addition most of them were somewhat satisfied or satisfied (100% of farmers and 66.6% of crop consultants) with the service and considered it a good value (62.5% of farmers and 66.7% of crop consultants). Both farmers and crop consultants were using APOLLO’s irrigation scheduling mostly on a weekly basis (62.5% and 66.7% accordingly). Most of the farmers (75%) found the service somewhat satisfactory,

while most of crop consultants (67%) found it very satisfactory in terms of quality. Also, both groups found the service to provide somewhat accurate and accurate results. When both groups asked if they faced any difficulties on learning using the service most of the farmers (62.5%) answered it was very easy for them while most of crop consultants (67%) answered it was not difficult for them. In addition, both groups agreed that APOLLO’s irrigation scheduling service proved to be practical and helped them to solve their tasks without additional effort and provided predictable results (87.5% of farmers and 100% of crop consultants) that made them feel they were in control when using the service. Most practitioners from both groups (87.5% of farmers and 66.7% of crop consultants) found very interesting to use this service while most of them like to use it. Crop consultants gave different answers (33.3% answered about the same performance, 33.3% answered that irrigation scheduling service had better performance and the rest answered that they had much better performance) regarding their awareness on APOLLO’s irrigation scheduling performance compared to other methods of irrigation scheduling that they knew of (e.g. based on their experience and based on the use of soil moisture sensors), while most farmers (62.5%) found better performance when using this service. Consequently, most people of these two groups (87.5% of farmers and 66.7% of crop consultants) were willing to purchase the APOLLO irrigation scheduling service for using it for next season and they would probably suggest it to their friends (50% of farmers and 66.7% of crop consultants). The questionnaire results on APOLLO’s irrigation scheduling service can be seen in [Table 3](#).

Table 3 – Questionnaire results on APOLLO’s irrigation scheduling service

Irrigation Scheduling Service	
Farmers	Crop Consultants
<p>A horizontal bar chart for Farmers showing 100% for 'Yes' and 0% for 'No'. The x-axis ranges from 0% to 100% in 20% increments.</p>	<p>A horizontal bar chart for Crop Consultants showing 100% for 'Yes' and 0% for 'No'. The x-axis ranges from 0% to 100% in 20% increments.</p>
<p>Q28 Did the Irrigation Scheduling Service help you to better organize your / your clients' irrigation operations?</p>	
<p>A horizontal bar chart for Farmers showing 100% for 'Yes' and 0% for 'No'. The x-axis ranges from 0% to 100% in 20% increments.</p>	<p>A horizontal bar chart for Crop Consultants showing 100% for 'Yes' and 0% for 'No'. The x-axis ranges from 0% to 100% in 20% increments.</p>
<p>Q29 Was the irrigation operation using APOLLO advice more effective than the reference one?</p>	

Q30 Do you find irrigation scheduling service useful?

Q31 Was the irrigation using APOLLO advice more effective than how you irrigate /advice for irrigation without APOLLO?

Q32 Did the Irrigation Scheduling Service help you to decrease your / your clients' water consumption on irrigation operations?

Irrigation Scheduling Service																																	
Farmers	Crop Consultants																																
Q33 Are you satisfied with the way APOLLO irrigation scheduling service performed?																																	
<p>A horizontal bar chart showing satisfaction levels for Farmers. The x-axis ranges from 0% to 80%. The y-axis categories are 'An exceptional value', 'A good value', and 'A poor value'. The bars show approximately 25% for 'An exceptional value', 65% for 'A good value', and 10% for 'A poor value'.</p> <table border="1"> <tr><th>Category</th><th>Percentage</th></tr> <tr><td>An exceptional value</td><td>25%</td></tr> <tr><td>A good value</td><td>65%</td></tr> <tr><td>A poor value</td><td>10%</td></tr> </table>	Category	Percentage	An exceptional value	25%	A good value	65%	A poor value	10%	<p>A horizontal bar chart showing satisfaction levels for Crop Consultants. The x-axis ranges from 0% to 80%. The y-axis categories are 'An exceptional value', 'A good value', and 'A poor value'. The bars show approximately 35% for 'An exceptional value', 65% for 'A good value', and 0% for 'A poor value'.</p> <table border="1"> <tr><th>Category</th><th>Percentage</th></tr> <tr><td>An exceptional value</td><td>35%</td></tr> <tr><td>A good value</td><td>65%</td></tr> <tr><td>A poor value</td><td>0%</td></tr> </table>	Category	Percentage	An exceptional value	35%	A good value	65%	A poor value	0%																
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Q34 Considering the overall value of the irrigation scheduling service, was it...																																	
<p>A horizontal bar chart showing usage frequency for Farmers. The x-axis ranges from 0% to 80%. The y-axis categories are 'Do not use', '2-3 times a year', 'Every 2-3 months', 'Once a month', 'Weekly', 'Daily', and 'Once a year'. The bars show approximately 10% for '2-3 times a year', 60% for 'Weekly', and 20% for 'Daily'.</p> <table border="1"> <tr><th>Category</th><th>Percentage</th></tr> <tr><td>Do not use</td><td>0%</td></tr> <tr><td>2-3 times a year</td><td>10%</td></tr> <tr><td>Every 2-3 months</td><td>0%</td></tr> <tr><td>Once a month</td><td>0%</td></tr> <tr><td>Weekly</td><td>60%</td></tr> <tr><td>Daily</td><td>20%</td></tr> <tr><td>Once a year</td><td>0%</td></tr> </table>	Category	Percentage	Do not use	0%	2-3 times a year	10%	Every 2-3 months	0%	Once a month	0%	Weekly	60%	Daily	20%	Once a year	0%	<p>A horizontal bar chart showing usage frequency for Crop Consultants. The x-axis ranges from 0% to 80%. The y-axis categories are 'Do not use', '2-3 times a year', 'Every 2-3 months', 'Once a month', 'Weekly', 'Daily', and 'Once a year'. The bars show approximately 65% for 'Weekly' and 30% for 'Daily'.</p> <table border="1"> <tr><th>Category</th><th>Percentage</th></tr> <tr><td>Do not use</td><td>0%</td></tr> <tr><td>2-3 times a year</td><td>0%</td></tr> <tr><td>Every 2-3 months</td><td>0%</td></tr> <tr><td>Once a month</td><td>0%</td></tr> <tr><td>Weekly</td><td>65%</td></tr> <tr><td>Daily</td><td>30%</td></tr> <tr><td>Once a year</td><td>0%</td></tr> </table>	Category	Percentage	Do not use	0%	2-3 times a year	0%	Every 2-3 months	0%	Once a month	0%	Weekly	65%	Daily	30%	Once a year	0%
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Q36 What is your impression on the overall quality of the information provided by the irrigation scheduling service?																																	
<p>A horizontal bar chart showing accuracy levels for Farmers. The x-axis ranges from 0% to 80%. The y-axis categories are 'Very Accurate', 'Accurate', 'Somewhat accurate', and 'Not accurate'. The bars show approximately 70% for 'Accurate', 25% for 'Somewhat accurate', and 0% for 'Very Accurate' and 'Not accurate'.</p> <table border="1"> <tr><th>Category</th><th>Percentage</th></tr> <tr><td>Very Accurate</td><td>0%</td></tr> <tr><td>Accurate</td><td>70%</td></tr> <tr><td>Somewhat accurate</td><td>25%</td></tr> <tr><td>Not accurate</td><td>0%</td></tr> </table>	Category	Percentage	Very Accurate	0%	Accurate	70%	Somewhat accurate	25%	Not accurate	0%	<p>A horizontal bar chart showing accuracy levels for Crop Consultants. The x-axis ranges from 0% to 60%. The y-axis categories are 'Very Accurate', 'Accurate', 'Somewhat accurate', and 'Not accurate'. The bars show 50% for 'Accurate', 50% for 'Somewhat accurate', and 0% for 'Very Accurate' and 'Not accurate'.</p> <table border="1"> <tr><th>Category</th><th>Percentage</th></tr> <tr><td>Very Accurate</td><td>0%</td></tr> <tr><td>Accurate</td><td>50%</td></tr> <tr><td>Somewhat accurate</td><td>50%</td></tr> <tr><td>Not accurate</td><td>0%</td></tr> </table>	Category	Percentage	Very Accurate	0%	Accurate	50%	Somewhat accurate	50%	Not accurate	0%												
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2.5 Crop Growth Monitoring Service

All farmers and crop consultants answered that APOLLO’s crop growth monitoring service helped them to better organize their crop scouting activities and that APOLLO’s advice was more effective compared to current methods of visits in the field, helping them also decrease the time they spent on crop scouting. Regarding the usefulness of the service, most farmers found it useful (55.6%) compared to 66.7% of crop consultants that found it very useful. Thus, all crop consultants were somewhat satisfied or satisfied, while most of them agree that the overall value of crop growth monitoring service is considered as good and exceptional (88.8% of farmers and 100% of crop consultants respectively). Also, 66.7% of each group answered that they advise APOLLO’s crop growth monitoring service in a weekly basis. Most farmers (77.8%) and all crop consultants answered that their impression for the service was very satisfactory, while they found it accurate (62.5% of farmers and 100% of crop consultants). Moreover, most farmers (55.6%) and all crop consultants answered that it wasn’t difficult for them to learn using this APOLLO service and the service provided them practical information on crop growth monitoring (66.7% of farmers and crop consultants). They answered also that they received predictable results, while it was very interesting for most of them to use this service (55.6% of farmers and 66.7% of crop consultants) and they like using it (55.6% of farmers and 66.7% of crop consultants). Most farmers answered that they received about the same results or better results from other methods of crop growth monitoring (e.g. field crop scouting, based on their experience) while the answers of crop consultants varied significantly. Finally, most farmers and crop consultants expressed their will on purchasing the APOLLO’s crop growth monitoring service for using it on next season (77.8% and 66.7% accordingly) while they would definitely suggest this service to their friends (44.4% of farmers and 66.7% of crop consultants). The questionnaire results on APOLLO’s crop growth monitoring service can be seen in [Table 4](#).

Table 4 – Questionnaire results on APOLLO crop growth monitoring service

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Q57 During crop growth monitoring, did this service help you solve your tasks without additional effort?																					
<table border="1"> <caption>Q57 - Farmers</caption> <thead> <tr> <th>Category</th> <th>Percentage</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Very predictable</td> <td>0%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Predictable</td> <td>80%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Somewhat unpredictable</td> <td>20%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Unpredictable</td> <td>0%</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Category	Percentage	Very predictable	0%	Predictable	80%	Somewhat unpredictable	20%	Unpredictable	0%	<table border="1"> <caption>Q57 - Crop Consultants</caption> <thead> <tr> <th>Category</th> <th>Percentage</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Very predictable</td> <td>35%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Predictable</td> <td>65%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Somewhat unpredictable</td> <td>0%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Unpredictable</td> <td>0%</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Category	Percentage	Very predictable	35%	Predictable	65%	Somewhat unpredictable	0%	Unpredictable	0%
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Q58 Do you feel you are in control when using this service?																					

2.6 Crop Yield Estimation Service

All farmers and crop consultants confirmed that crop yield estimation service helped them to better organize crop harvesting operation and provided more effective advices compared to their current method. In addition, both groups confirmed that this service is useful to them and helped them decrease their times on crop yield estimation operations. Most of crop consultants (66.7%) and farmers (44.4%) answered that this service is somewhat satisfactory and provides a good value to them by using it (66.7% and 77.8% accordingly). Regarding the frequency of using this service, most farmers were informed from it once a week before harvest (55.6%), while all crop consultants were informed more than once a week before harvest. While farmers found that APOLLO's crop yield estimation service provided them somewhat satisfactory (50%) quality and somewhat accurate (57.1%) estimations, in contrast most crop consultants answered that they received very satisfactory (100%) quality and accurate (66.7%) crop yield estimations. Most of crop consultants found the service very practical (66.7%) and predictable (66.7%) regarding its results, while most farmers found it practical (66.7%) and predictable (88.9%). Most farmers and crop consultants agreed that it is interesting to use this service (66.7% and 66.7% accordingly) and they like using it (55.6% and 100% accordingly). Finally, both groups agreed that crop yield estimation service is better than other methods of crop yield estimation (e.g. in field destructive methods) (75% of farmers and 100% of crop consultants) and consequently they will purchase this service for using it for the next season (77.8% of farmers and 100% of crop consultants) as well as probably recommending it to their friends (44.4% of farmers and 66.7% of crop consultants). The questionnaire results on APOLLO's crop yield estimation service can be seen in [Table 1](#)[Table 5](#)[Table 5](#).

Table 5 – Questionnaire results on APOLLO crop yield estimation service

Crop Yield Estimation Service	
Farmers	Crop Consultants
<p>A horizontal bar chart for Farmers showing 100% for 'Yes' and 0% for 'No'. The x-axis ranges from 0% to 100% in 20% increments.</p>	<p>A horizontal bar chart for Crop Consultants showing 100% for 'Yes' and 0% for 'No'. The x-axis ranges from 0% to 100% in 20% increments.</p>
<p>Q64 Did the Crop Yield Estimation Service help you to better organize your / your clients crop harvesting operations?</p>	
<p>A horizontal bar chart for Farmers showing approximately 95% for 'Yes' and 5% for 'No'. The x-axis ranges from 0% to 100% in 20% increments.</p>	<p>A horizontal bar chart for Crop Consultants showing approximately 95% for 'Yes' and 5% for 'No'. The x-axis ranges from 0% to 100% in 20% increments.</p>
<p>Q65 Was the crop harvesting operation using APOLLO advice more effective than the reference one?</p>	
<p>A horizontal bar chart for Farmers showing approximately 35% for 'Very Useful', 65% for 'Useful', and 0% for 'Not Useful'. The x-axis ranges from 0% to 80% in 20% increments.</p>	<p>A horizontal bar chart for Crop Consultants showing 100% for 'Useful', 0% for 'Very Useful', and 0% for 'Not Useful'. The x-axis ranges from 0% to 120% in 20% increments.</p>
<p>Q66 Do you find crop yield estimation service useful?</p>	
<p>A horizontal bar chart for Farmers showing approximately 90% for 'Yes' and 10% for 'No'. The x-axis ranges from 0% to 100% in 20% increments.</p>	<p>A horizontal bar chart for Crop Consultants showing 100% for 'Yes' and 0% for 'No'. The x-axis ranges from 0% to 100% in 20% increments.</p>

Crop Yield Estimation Service																									
Farmers	Crop Consultants																								
<p>Q67 Was the crop yield estimation operation using APOLLO advice more effective than how you estimate your crop yields without APOLLO?</p>																									
<table border="1"> <caption>Q67 Farmers Data</caption> <thead> <tr> <th>Response</th> <th>Percentage</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>No</td> <td>12%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Yes</td> <td>88%</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Response	Percentage	No	12%	Yes	88%	<table border="1"> <caption>Q67 Crop Consultants Data</caption> <thead> <tr> <th>Response</th> <th>Percentage</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>No</td> <td>0%</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Yes</td> <td>100%</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Response	Percentage	No	0%	Yes	100%												
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<p>Q68 Did the crop yield estimation service help you to decrease your time on crop yield estimation operations?</p>																									
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<p>Q72 What is your impression on the overall quality of the information provided by the crop yield estimation service?</p>																									
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<p>Q73 How accurate did you find the information provided by the service?</p>																									
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<p>Q74 How easy was it to learn using this APOLLO service?</p>																									

2.7 APOLLO Platform

Most farmers and crop consultants answered that they are somewhat satisfied or satisfied from the APOLLO platform (88.9% and 66.6% accordingly). Consequently, they believe that APOLLO platform has a good value as a tool for their work (87.5% of farmers and 66.7% of crop consultants). More than 60% of both groups stated that they found the performance of APOLLO platform very satisfactory while it was not difficult for them to learn using it (44.4% of the farmers and 66.7% of the crop consultants). Regarding their usage experience, most farmers found it somewhat satisfactory, while the answers of crop consultants on that varied significantly among them. However, both groups based on their knowledge agreed that APOLLO platform was better than other methods and platforms that are used currently on agriculture (87.5% of farmers and 66.7% of crop consultants). Based on

the aforementioned question, most of the farmers (77.8%) answered that will probably be customers of the APOLLO platform, while crop consultants gave different answers. Consequently, most farmers and crop consultants most probably would recommend APOLLO platform to their friends even if most of them faced difficulties using APOLLO platform (55.6% of farmers and 66.7% of crop consultants). The questionnaire results on APOLLO platform can be seen in [Table 6](#).

Table 6 – Questionnaire results on APOLLO platform

APOLLO Platform																									
Farmers	Crop Consultants																								
<table border="1"> <caption>Satisfaction Levels - Farmers</caption> <tr><th>Satisfaction Level</th><th>Percentage</th></tr> <tr><td>Satisfied</td><td>55.6%</td></tr> <tr><td>Somewhat Satisfied</td><td>22.2%</td></tr> <tr><td>Neither Satisfied nor Satisfied</td><td>11.1%</td></tr> <tr><td>Somewhat Unsatisfied</td><td>7.8%</td></tr> <tr><td>Unsatisfied</td><td>2.3%</td></tr> </table>	Satisfaction Level	Percentage	Satisfied	55.6%	Somewhat Satisfied	22.2%	Neither Satisfied nor Satisfied	11.1%	Somewhat Unsatisfied	7.8%	Unsatisfied	2.3%	<table border="1"> <caption>Satisfaction Levels - Crop Consultants</caption> <tr><th>Satisfaction Level</th><th>Percentage</th></tr> <tr><td>Satisfied</td><td>33.3%</td></tr> <tr><td>Somewhat Satisfied</td><td>33.3%</td></tr> <tr><td>Neither Satisfied nor Satisfied</td><td>33.3%</td></tr> <tr><td>Somewhat Unsatisfied</td><td>0%</td></tr> <tr><td>Unsatisfied</td><td>0%</td></tr> </table>	Satisfaction Level	Percentage	Satisfied	33.3%	Somewhat Satisfied	33.3%	Neither Satisfied nor Satisfied	33.3%	Somewhat Unsatisfied	0%	Unsatisfied	0%
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Q82 Are you satisfied with the way APOLLO platform performed?																									
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Q83 Considering the overall value of the APOLLO platform, was it...																									
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Q84 How did APOLLO platform perform regarding overall quality?																									

Q85 How easy was to learn using APOLLO platform?

Q86 How did APOLLO platform perform regarding usage experience?

Q87 Based on your awareness on APOLLO platform, is it better, the same, or worse than other methods and platforms?

Q88 Based on your experience with APOLLO platform, how likely are you to be a customer of APOLLO platform (if the price is reasonable)?

3 Future Work

The complete evaluation of APOLLO platform and APOLLO services need to include some quantitative results despite of the questionnaire results that were presented in this document. This will be done **by conducting field trials** to the pilot areas of the APOLLO project as these are mentioned on the evaluation plan that exists on Deliverable 6.1 - Pilot plan and evaluation methodology. The APOLLO services will be tested regarding usability, accessibility, reliability and the degree of satisfaction for end users. Moreover, **additional users will test and evaluate APOLLO services in order to widen the evaluation process** and receive more feedback regarding platform and services development. Finally APOLLO platform **will be evaluated in terms of accessibility and reliability of the platform** based on appropriate metrics coming from APOLLO server. This work will be presented in the upcoming deliverables D6.6 – 2nd Intermediate Evaluation Report and D6.7 – Validation Report.

4 Conclusions

In this document it is presented the work that was conducted for evaluating the APOLLO platform and services through a questionnaire survey under the WP6 – Pilot Operation and Evaluation. The

questionnaire survey was conducted by involving only the alpha users of the APOLLO platform (farmers and crop consultants) in order to provide a qualitative assessment while they answered on the usefulness and accuracy of the services based on their experience. Aim of this study was to identify the user acceptance in terms of reliability, of good usability experience and degree of satisfaction for each service and the platform before widening the evaluation of the aforementioned by conducting field experiments and providing access to other beta phase users. The field trials will help also to verify the findings of this questionnaire survey regarding the benefit that the farmers and crop consultants can have by using APOLLO services.

Regarding APOLLO services, it seemed that all services were considered useful for the users, with crop consultants to be mostly in favor with irrigation scheduling and crop growth monitoring as they found it more useful for their agronomic advices to the farmers. In terms of easiness to learn most of the services were considered easy/very easy to become understandable, while in terms of accuracy the farmers found every service accurate (except yield estimation) with the consultants to find more accurate yield estimation and crop growth monitoring services, which both values are being extracted using NDVI measurements.

Regarding the platform, both farmers and crop consultants answered that APOLLO platform has a very satisfactory quality, by providing an overall good value for their needs. In addition, both of the user groups believed that the platform is not difficult to be learned and that is providing better results than other platforms. This makes them to believe that they would probably recommend the final platform to their friends/colleagues.

Based on the findings, all APOLLO services as well as the APOLLO platform presented high acceptance, reliability, good usability experience and degree of satisfaction. However, each service presented different degree of usability, acceptance and reliability according to the alpha users. These findings will help the APOLLO consortium to refine more the evaluation processes that will follow in the upcoming months in terms of field trials and questionnaire surveys.

5 References

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6 Annexes

6.1 Annex I: Instructions for Evaluation Event

Introduction

Aim of this event is to present the updated version of APOLLO platform and conduct the evaluation of the beta version of APOLLO services. **ONLY alpha users (farmers and consultants/cooperatives) should be involved (at least one consultant)**. This event consists of three different parts that are described below.

Part 1: Demonstration of the APOLLO platform

The first part is a short demonstration of the APOLLO platform. Shadows (from pilot partner or supporting technical partner) should present the updated APOLLO platform as well as its functionalities to the alpha users.

Duration: approx. 20-30 minutes

Part 2: Hands on the APOLLO platform

At this section the alpha users should try and test the APOLLO services and their functionalities with the support of the shadows. The alpha users should try all three services: tillage scheduling, irrigation scheduling, crop growth monitoring and yield estimation, BUT focus should be on crop growth monitoring and yield estimation.

After login to their accounts, the farmers should test the services on their pilot parcels declared for the agricultural season 2017.

Tillage and irrigation scheduling service: Farmers should look at the information provided by these services and the functionalities of the application and estimate the usability and usefulness of the services. **Quality of the information provided should not be evaluated because soil moisture model it is still under development.**

Crop growth monitoring service: Farmers should check crop growth parameter maps (NDVI, LAI, Chl, biomass) and graphs in various growth stages during the previous season (2017) for the pilot parcels. They should compare the information received from the APOLLO service with their own experience and identify the usability and usefulness of the service and quality of the information.

Yield estimation service: Farmers should check the information on the estimated yield for their parcels during the previous season (2017) and compare it with the real yield values (measured after the harvest). Farmers should provide the data of the measured total yield on the pilot parcels in 2017.

Duration: 60-90 minutes

Part 3: Evaluation Questionnaire completion

The alpha users should complete the evaluation questionnaire after finishing the hands on experience of the APOLLO platform. Please note that there are 2 versions of the questionnaire: for farmers and for consultants/cooperatives. Shadows should guide the alpha users through the questionnaire, provide explanation if needed and record the answers. It is also important to record any additional remarks and comments made by the participants.

Duration: approx. 45-60 minutes

6.2 Annex II: Questionnaire for Farmers

The APOLLO project is conducting a survey in order to evaluate APOLLO Platform. The APOLLO platform collects and analyses satellite data in order to offer added value services to small farmers, crop consultants and agricultural cooperatives. The offered services are tillage scheduling service, irrigation scheduling service, crop growth monitoring service and yield estimation service.

Q1	Questionnaire ID:	
Q2	Survey Date:	

Demographics					
Q3	Area and country:				
Q4	What is your age group?				
	18-34 <input type="checkbox"/>	35-44 <input type="checkbox"/>	45-54 <input type="checkbox"/>	55-64 <input type="checkbox"/>	65+ <input type="checkbox"/>
Q5	What is your gender?				
	Male <input type="checkbox"/>			Female <input type="checkbox"/>	
Q6	What is your education level?				
	Primary <input type="checkbox"/>	Secondary <input type="checkbox"/>	Graduate <input type="checkbox"/>	Post Graduate <input type="checkbox"/>	

General Information				
Q7	For what kind of crops did you use APOLLO platform services?			
	Arable Crops <input type="checkbox"/>	Orchards <input type="checkbox"/>	Open Field Vegetables <input type="checkbox"/>	
Q8	Which are the crops for which you used APOLLO platform services?			
	1.	2.	3.	
	4.	5.	6.	
Q9	What is the total area for which you used APOLLO platform services?			
	Less than 10 ha <input type="checkbox"/>	10-30 ha <input type="checkbox"/>	30-60 ha <input type="checkbox"/>	60-90 ha <input type="checkbox"/>

Tillage Scheduling Service		
Q10	Did the Tillage Scheduling Service help you to better organize your tillage operations?	
	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>	No <input type="checkbox"/>
Q11	Was the tillage operation using APOLLO advice more effective than the reference one?	
	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>	No <input type="checkbox"/>
Q12	Do you find tillage scheduling service useful?	
	Not Useful <input type="checkbox"/>	Useful <input type="checkbox"/>
Q13	Was the tillage operation using APOLLO advice more effective than how you tillage without APOLLO?	
	Yes	No

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	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Q14	Did the Tillage Scheduling Service help you to decrease your fuel consumption on tillage operations?						
	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>				No <input type="checkbox"/>		
Q15	Are you satisfied with the way APOLLO tillage scheduling service performed?						
	Unsatisfied <input type="checkbox"/>	Somewhat Unsatisfied <input type="checkbox"/>	Neither Satisfied nor Satisfied <input type="checkbox"/>	Somewhat Satisfied <input type="checkbox"/>	Satisfied <input type="checkbox"/>		
Q16	Considering the overall value of the tillage scheduling service, was it...						
	A poor value <input type="checkbox"/>	A good value <input type="checkbox"/>		An exceptional value <input type="checkbox"/>			
Q17	How often did you typically use the tillage scheduling service?						
	Once a year <input type="checkbox"/>	Daily <input type="checkbox"/>	Weekly <input type="checkbox"/>	Once a month <input type="checkbox"/>	Every 2-3 months <input type="checkbox"/>	2-3 times a year <input type="checkbox"/>	Do not use <input type="checkbox"/>
Q18	What is your impression on the overall quality of the information provided by the tillage scheduling service?						
	Miserable <input type="checkbox"/>	Somewhat Satisfactory <input type="checkbox"/>	Very Satisfactory <input type="checkbox"/>		Delightful <input type="checkbox"/>		
Q19	How accurate did you find the information provided by the service?						
	Not accurate <input type="checkbox"/>	Somewhat accurate <input type="checkbox"/>	Accurate <input type="checkbox"/>		Very Accurate <input type="checkbox"/>		
Q20	How easy was it to learn using this APOLLO service?						
	Hard to learn <input type="checkbox"/>	Somewhat Difficult <input type="checkbox"/>		Not difficult <input type="checkbox"/>	Very Easy <input type="checkbox"/>		
Q21	During tillage, did this service help you solve your tasks without additional effort?						
	Not practical <input type="checkbox"/>	Somewhat practical <input type="checkbox"/>		Practical <input type="checkbox"/>	Very practical <input type="checkbox"/>		
Q22	Do you feel you are in control when using this service?						
	Unpredictable <input type="checkbox"/>	Somewhat unpredictable <input type="checkbox"/>		Predictable <input type="checkbox"/>	Very predictable <input type="checkbox"/>		
Q23	Is it exciting and motivating to use this service?						
	Dull <input type="checkbox"/>	Somewhat dull <input type="checkbox"/>		Interesting <input type="checkbox"/>	Very interesting <input type="checkbox"/>		
Q24	What is your overall impression of the service?						
	I don't like it <input type="checkbox"/>	I somewhat don't like it <input type="checkbox"/>		I somewhat like it <input type="checkbox"/>	I like it <input type="checkbox"/>		
Q25	Based on your awareness on tillage scheduling service, is it better, the same, or worse than other methods of tillage scheduling?						
	Much Worse <input type="checkbox"/>	Worse <input type="checkbox"/>	About the same <input type="checkbox"/>	Better <input type="checkbox"/>	Much Better <input type="checkbox"/>		
Q26	Based on your experience with tillage scheduling service, which of the following are you most likely to do for the next season?						
	Return to how I was tilling before <input type="checkbox"/>	Explore available tillage support options on the market <input type="checkbox"/>		Purchase APOLLO tillage scheduling service <input type="checkbox"/>			
Q27	Based on your experience with tillage scheduling service, would you recommend this service to a friend?						
	Definitely will not <input type="checkbox"/>	Probably will not <input type="checkbox"/>	Might or might not <input type="checkbox"/>	Probably will <input type="checkbox"/>	Definitely will <input type="checkbox"/>		

Irrigation Scheduling Service						
Q28	Did the Irrigation Scheduling Service help you to better organize your irrigation operations?					
	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>			No <input type="checkbox"/>		
Q29	Was the irrigation operation using APOLLO advice more effective than the reference one?					
	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>			No <input type="checkbox"/>		
Q30	Do you find irrigation scheduling service useful?					
	Not Useful <input type="checkbox"/>		Useful <input type="checkbox"/>		Very Useful <input type="checkbox"/>	
Q31	Was the irrigation operation using APOLLO advice more effective than how you irrigate without APOLLO?					
	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>			No <input type="checkbox"/>		
Q32	Did the Irrigation Scheduling Service help you to decrease your water consumption on irrigation operations?					
	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>			No <input type="checkbox"/>		
Q33	Are you satisfied with the way APOLLO irrigation scheduling service performed?					
	Unsatisfied <input type="checkbox"/>	Somewhat Unsatisfied <input type="checkbox"/>	Neither Satisfied nor Satisfied <input type="checkbox"/>	Somewhat Satisfied <input type="checkbox"/>	Satisfied <input type="checkbox"/>	
Q34	Considering the overall value of the irrigation scheduling service, was it...					
	A poor value <input type="checkbox"/>		A good value <input type="checkbox"/>		An exceptional value <input type="checkbox"/>	
Q35	How often did you typically use the irrigation scheduling service?					
	Once a year <input type="checkbox"/>	Daily <input type="checkbox"/>	Weekly <input type="checkbox"/>	Once a month <input type="checkbox"/>	Every 2-3 months <input type="checkbox"/>	2-3 times a year <input type="checkbox"/>
Q36	What is your impression on the overall quality of the information provided by the irrigation scheduling service?					
	Miserable <input type="checkbox"/>	Somewhat Satisfactory <input type="checkbox"/>		Very Satisfactory <input type="checkbox"/>		Delightful <input type="checkbox"/>
Q37	How accurate did you find the information provided by the service?					
	Not accurate <input type="checkbox"/>	Somewhat accurate <input type="checkbox"/>		Accurate <input type="checkbox"/>		Very Accurate <input type="checkbox"/>
Q38	How easy was it to learn using this APOLLO service?					
	Hard to learn <input type="checkbox"/>	Somewhat Difficult <input type="checkbox"/>		Not difficult <input type="checkbox"/>		Very Easy <input type="checkbox"/>
Q39	During irrigation, did this service help you solve your tasks without additional effort?					
	Not practical <input type="checkbox"/>	Somewhat practical <input type="checkbox"/>		Practical <input type="checkbox"/>		Very practical <input type="checkbox"/>
Q40	Do you feel you are in control when using this service?					
	Unpredictable <input type="checkbox"/>	Somewhat unpredictable <input type="checkbox"/>		Predictable <input type="checkbox"/>		Very predictable <input type="checkbox"/>
Q41	Is it exciting and motivating to use this service?					
	Dull <input type="checkbox"/>	Somewhat dull <input type="checkbox"/>		Interesting <input type="checkbox"/>		Very interesting <input type="checkbox"/>
Q42	What is your overall impression of the service?					
	I don't like it <input type="checkbox"/>	I somewhat don't like it <input type="checkbox"/>		I somewhat like it <input type="checkbox"/>		I like it <input type="checkbox"/>

Q43	Based on your awareness on irrigation scheduling service, is it better, the same, or worse than other methods of irrigation scheduling?					
	Much Worse <input type="checkbox"/>	Worse <input type="checkbox"/>	About the same <input type="checkbox"/>	Better <input type="checkbox"/>	Much Better <input type="checkbox"/>	
Q44	Based on your experience with irrigation scheduling service, which of the following are you most likely to do for the next season?					
	Return to how I was irrigating before <input type="checkbox"/>	Explore available irrigation support options on the market <input type="checkbox"/>		Purchase APOLLO irrigation scheduling service <input type="checkbox"/>		
Q45	Based on your experience with irrigation scheduling service, would you recommend this service to a friend?					
	Definitely will not <input type="checkbox"/>	Probably will not <input type="checkbox"/>	Might or might not <input type="checkbox"/>	Probably will <input type="checkbox"/>	Definitely will <input type="checkbox"/>	
Crop Growth Monitoring Service						
Q46	Did the Crop Growth Monitoring Service help you to better organize your crop growth monitoring operations?					
	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>			No <input type="checkbox"/>		
Q47	Was the crop growth monitoring operation using APOLLO advice more effective than the reference one?					
	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>			No <input type="checkbox"/>		
Q48	Do you find crop growth monitoring service useful?					
	Not Useful <input type="checkbox"/>	Useful <input type="checkbox"/>		Very Useful <input type="checkbox"/>		
Q49	Was the crop growth monitoring operation using APOLLO advice more effective than how you monitor your crops without APOLLO?					
	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>			No <input type="checkbox"/>		
Q50	Did the crop growth monitoring Service help you to decrease your time on crop growth monitoring operations?					
	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>			No <input type="checkbox"/>		
Q51	Are you satisfied with the way APOLLO crop growth monitoring service performed?					
	Unsatisfied <input type="checkbox"/>	Somewhat Unsatisfied <input type="checkbox"/>	Neither Satisfied nor Satisfied <input type="checkbox"/>	Somewhat Satisfied <input type="checkbox"/>	Satisfied <input type="checkbox"/>	
Q52	Considering the overall value of the crop growth monitoring service, was it...					
	A poor value <input type="checkbox"/>		A good value <input type="checkbox"/>		An exceptional value <input type="checkbox"/>	
Q53	How often did you typically use the crop growth monitoring service?					
	Once a year <input type="checkbox"/>	Daily <input type="checkbox"/>	Weekly <input type="checkbox"/>	Once a month <input type="checkbox"/>	Every 2-3 months <input type="checkbox"/>	2-3 times a year <input type="checkbox"/>
Q54	What is your impression on the overall quality of the information provided by the crop growth monitoring service?					
	Miserable <input type="checkbox"/>	Somewhat Satisfactory <input type="checkbox"/>		Very Satisfactory <input type="checkbox"/>		Delightful <input type="checkbox"/>
Q55	How accurate did you find the information provided by the service?					
	Not accurate <input type="checkbox"/>	Somewhat accurate <input type="checkbox"/>		Accurate <input type="checkbox"/>		Very Accurate <input type="checkbox"/>
Q56	How easy was it to learn using this APOLLO service?					
	Hard to learn <input type="checkbox"/>	Somewhat Difficult <input type="checkbox"/>		Not difficult <input type="checkbox"/>		Very Easy <input type="checkbox"/>

Q57	During crop growth monitoring, did this service help you solve your tasks without additional effort?			
	Not practical <input type="checkbox"/>	Somewhat practical <input type="checkbox"/>	Practical <input type="checkbox"/>	Very practical <input type="checkbox"/>
Q58	Do you feel you are in control when using this service?			
	Unpredictable <input type="checkbox"/>	Somewhat unpredictable <input type="checkbox"/>	Predictable <input type="checkbox"/>	Very predictable <input type="checkbox"/>
Q59	Is it exciting and motivating to use this service?			
	Dull <input type="checkbox"/>	Somewhat dull <input type="checkbox"/>	Interesting <input type="checkbox"/>	Very interesting <input type="checkbox"/>
Q60	What is your overall impression of the service?			
	I don't like it <input type="checkbox"/>	I somewhat don't like it <input type="checkbox"/>	I somewhat like it <input type="checkbox"/>	I like it <input type="checkbox"/>
Q61	Based on your awareness on crop growth monitoring service, is it better, the same, or worse than other methods of crop growth monitoring?			
	Much Worse <input type="checkbox"/>	Worse <input type="checkbox"/>	About the same <input type="checkbox"/>	Better <input type="checkbox"/>
Q62	Based on your experience with crop growth monitoring service, which of the following are you most likely to do for the next season?			
	Return to how I was crop scouting before <input type="checkbox"/>	Explore available crop growth monitoring support options on the market <input type="checkbox"/>	Purchase APOLLO crop growth monitoring service <input type="checkbox"/>	
Q63	Based on your experience with crop growth monitoring service, would you recommend this service to a friend?			
	Definitely will not <input type="checkbox"/>	Probably will not <input type="checkbox"/>	Might or might not <input type="checkbox"/>	Probably will <input type="checkbox"/>
Crop Yield Estimation Service				
Q64	Did the Crop Yield Estimation Service help you to better organize your crop harvesting operations?			
	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>		No <input type="checkbox"/>	
Q65	Was the crop harvesting operation using APOLLO advice more effective than the reference one?			
	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>		No <input type="checkbox"/>	
Q66	Do you find crop yield estimation service useful?			
	Not Useful <input type="checkbox"/>	Useful <input type="checkbox"/>		Very Useful <input type="checkbox"/>
Q67	Was the crop yield estimation operation using APOLLO advice more effective than how you estimate your crop yields without APOLLO?			
	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>		No <input type="checkbox"/>	
Q68	Did the crop yield estimation service help you to decrease your time on crop yield estimation operations?			
	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>		No <input type="checkbox"/>	
Q69	Are you satisfied with the way APOLLO crop yield estimation service performed?			
	Unsatisfied <input type="checkbox"/>	Somewhat Unsatisfied <input type="checkbox"/>	Neither Satisfied nor Satisfied <input type="checkbox"/>	Somewhat Satisfied <input type="checkbox"/>
Q70	Considering the overall value of the crop yield estimation service, was it...			
	A poor value <input type="checkbox"/>	A good value <input type="checkbox"/>		An exceptional value <input type="checkbox"/>

Q71	How often did you typically use the crop yield estimation service?				
	Once <input type="checkbox"/>	Once a week at the end of the season <input type="checkbox"/>	More than once in week at the end of the season <input type="checkbox"/>	Once a month at the end of the season <input type="checkbox"/>	Do not use <input type="checkbox"/>
Q72	What is your impression on the overall quality of the information provided by the crop yield estimation service?				
	Miserable <input type="checkbox"/>	Somewhat Satisfactory <input type="checkbox"/>	Very Satisfactory <input type="checkbox"/>	Delightful <input type="checkbox"/>	
Q73	How accurate did you find the information provided by the service?				
	Not accurate <input type="checkbox"/>	Somewhat accurate <input type="checkbox"/>	Accurate <input type="checkbox"/>	Very Accurate <input type="checkbox"/>	
Q74	How easy was it to learn using this APOLLO service?				
	Hard to learn <input type="checkbox"/>	Somewhat Difficult <input type="checkbox"/>	Not difficult <input type="checkbox"/>	Very Easy <input type="checkbox"/>	
Q75	During crop yield estimation, did this service help you solve your tasks without additional effort?				
	Not practical <input type="checkbox"/>	Somewhat practical <input type="checkbox"/>	Practical <input type="checkbox"/>	Very practical <input type="checkbox"/>	
Q76	Do you feel you are in control when using this service?				
	Unpredictable <input type="checkbox"/>	Somewhat unpredictable <input type="checkbox"/>	Predictable <input type="checkbox"/>	Very predictable <input type="checkbox"/>	
Q77	Is it exciting and motivating to use this service?				
	Dull <input type="checkbox"/>	Somewhat dull <input type="checkbox"/>	Interesting <input type="checkbox"/>	Very interesting <input type="checkbox"/>	
Q78	What is your overall impression of the service?				
	I don't like it <input type="checkbox"/>	I somewhat don't like it <input type="checkbox"/>	I somewhat like it <input type="checkbox"/>	I like it <input type="checkbox"/>	
Q79	Based on your awareness on crop yield estimation service, is it better, the same, or worse than other methods of crop yield estimation?				
	Much Worse <input type="checkbox"/>	Worse <input type="checkbox"/>	About the same <input type="checkbox"/>	Better <input type="checkbox"/>	Much Better <input type="checkbox"/>
Q80	Based on your experience with crop yield estimation service, which of the following are you most likely to do for the next season?				
	Return to how I was estimating yield before <input type="checkbox"/>	Explore available crop yield estimation support options on the market <input type="checkbox"/>	Purchase APOLLO crop yield estimation service <input type="checkbox"/>		
Q81	Based on your experience with crop yield estimation service, would you recommend this service to a friend?				
	Definitely will not <input type="checkbox"/>	Probably will not <input type="checkbox"/>	Might or might not <input type="checkbox"/>	Probably will <input type="checkbox"/>	Definitely will <input type="checkbox"/>
APOLLO Platform					
Q82	Are you satisfied with the way APOLLO platform performed?				
	Unsatisfied <input type="checkbox"/>	Somewhat Unsatisfied <input type="checkbox"/>	Neither Satisfied nor Satisfied <input type="checkbox"/>	Somewhat Satisfied <input type="checkbox"/>	Satisfied <input type="checkbox"/>
Q83	Considering the overall value of the APOLLO platform, was it...				
	A poor value <input type="checkbox"/>	A good value <input type="checkbox"/>		An exceptional value <input type="checkbox"/>	
Q84	How did APOLLO platform perform regarding overall quality?				
	Miserably <input type="checkbox"/>	Somewhat Satisfactory <input type="checkbox"/>	Very Satisfactory <input type="checkbox"/>	Delightfully <input type="checkbox"/>	

Q85	How easy was to learn using APOLLO platform?			
	Hard to learn <input type="checkbox"/>	Somewhat Difficult <input type="checkbox"/>	Not difficult <input type="checkbox"/>	Very Easy <input type="checkbox"/>
Q86	How did APOLLO platform perform regarding usage experience?			
	Miserably <input type="checkbox"/>	Somewhat Satisfactory <input type="checkbox"/>	Very Satisfactory <input type="checkbox"/>	Delightfully <input type="checkbox"/>
Q87	Based on your awareness on APOLLO platform, is it better, the same, or worse than other methods and platforms?			
	Much Worse <input type="checkbox"/>	Worse <input type="checkbox"/>	About the same <input type="checkbox"/>	Better <input type="checkbox"/>
Q88	Based on your experience with APOLLO platform, how likely are you to be a customer of APOLLO platform (if the price is reasonable)?			
	Definitely will not <input type="checkbox"/>	Probably will not <input type="checkbox"/>	Might or might not <input type="checkbox"/>	Probably will <input type="checkbox"/>
Q89	Based on your experience with APOLLO platform, would you recommend this platform to a friend?			
	Definitely will not <input type="checkbox"/>	Probably will not <input type="checkbox"/>	Might or might not <input type="checkbox"/>	Probably will <input type="checkbox"/>
Q90	Did you experience any difficulties in using APOLLO platform?			
	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>		No <input type="checkbox"/>	

6.3 Annex III: Questionnaire for Crop Consultants

The APOLLO project is conducting a survey in order to evaluate APOLLO Platform. The APOLLO platform collects and analyses satellite data in order to offer added value services to small farmers, crop consultants and agricultural cooperatives. The offered services are tillage scheduling service, irrigation scheduling service, crop growth monitoring service and yield estimation service.

Q1	Questionnaire ID:	
Q2	Survey Date:	

Demographics				
Q3	Area and country:			
Q4	What is your age group?			
	18-34 <input type="checkbox"/>	35-44 <input type="checkbox"/>	45-54 <input type="checkbox"/>	55-64 <input type="checkbox"/>
Q5	What is your gender?			
	Male <input type="checkbox"/>		Female <input type="checkbox"/>	
Q6	What is your education level?			
	Primary <input type="checkbox"/>	Secondary <input type="checkbox"/>	Graduate <input type="checkbox"/>	Post Graduate <input type="checkbox"/>

General Information				
Q7	In what kind of crops did you use APOLLO platform services to provide advises to your clients/members?			
	Arable Crops <input type="checkbox"/>	Orchards <input type="checkbox"/>	Open Field Vegetables <input type="checkbox"/>	
Q8	Which are the crops that you use APOLLO platform services to provide advises to your clients/members?			
	1.	2.	3.	
	4.	5.	6.	
	7.	8.	9.	
Q9	What is the total area that you used APOLLO platform services?			
	Less than 100 ha <input type="checkbox"/>	100-300 ha <input type="checkbox"/>	300-600 ha <input type="checkbox"/>	600-900 ha <input type="checkbox"/>

Tillage Scheduling Service				
Q10	Did the Tillage Scheduling Service help you to better organize the tillage operations of your farmers/clients?			
	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>		No <input type="checkbox"/>	
Q11	Was the tillage operation using APOLLO advice more effective than the reference one?			
	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>		No <input type="checkbox"/>	
Q12	Do you find tillage scheduling service useful?			
	Not Useful <input type="checkbox"/>	Useful <input type="checkbox"/>	Very Useful <input type="checkbox"/>	
Q13	Was the tillage operation using APOLLO advice more effective than how you advice for tillage without APOLLO?			
	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>		No <input type="checkbox"/>	

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Q14	Did the Tillage Scheduling Service help your farmers/clients to decrease your fuel consumption on tillage operations?						
	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>		No <input type="checkbox"/>				
Q15	Are you satisfied with the way APOLLO tillage scheduling service performed?						
	Unsatisfied <input type="checkbox"/>	Somewhat Unsatisfied <input type="checkbox"/>	Neither Satisfied nor Satisfied <input type="checkbox"/>	Somewhat Satisfied <input type="checkbox"/>	Satisfied <input type="checkbox"/>		
Q16	Considering the overall value of the tillage scheduling service, was it...						
	A poor value <input type="checkbox"/>		A good value <input type="checkbox"/>		An exceptional value <input type="checkbox"/>		
Q17	How often did you typically use the tillage scheduling service?						
	Once a year <input type="checkbox"/>	Daily <input type="checkbox"/>	Weekly <input type="checkbox"/>	Once a month <input type="checkbox"/>	Every 2-3 months <input type="checkbox"/>	2-3 times a year <input type="checkbox"/>	Do not use <input type="checkbox"/>
Q18	What is your impression on the overall quality of the information provided by the tillage scheduling service?						
	Miserable <input type="checkbox"/>		Somewhat Satisfactory <input type="checkbox"/>		Very Satisfactory <input type="checkbox"/>		Delightful <input type="checkbox"/>
Q19	How accurate did you find the information provided by the service?						
	Not accurate <input type="checkbox"/>		Somewhat accurate <input type="checkbox"/>		Accurate <input type="checkbox"/>		Very Accurate <input type="checkbox"/>
Q20	How easy was it to learn using this APOLLO service?						
	Hard to learn <input type="checkbox"/>		Somewhat Difficult <input type="checkbox"/>		Not difficult <input type="checkbox"/>		Very Easy <input type="checkbox"/>
Q21	During tillage, did this service help your farmers/clients solve their tasks without additional effort?						
	Not practical <input type="checkbox"/>		Somewhat practical <input type="checkbox"/>		Practical <input type="checkbox"/>		Very practical <input type="checkbox"/>
Q22	Do you feel you are in control when using this service?						
	Unpredictable <input type="checkbox"/>		Somewhat unpredictable <input type="checkbox"/>		Predictable <input type="checkbox"/>		Very predictable <input type="checkbox"/>
Q23	Is it exciting and motivating to use this service?						
	Dull <input type="checkbox"/>		Somewhat dull <input type="checkbox"/>		Interesting <input type="checkbox"/>		Very interesting <input type="checkbox"/>
Q24	What is your overall impression of the service?						
	I don't like it <input type="checkbox"/>		I somewhat don't like it <input type="checkbox"/>		I somewhat like it <input type="checkbox"/>		I like it <input type="checkbox"/>
Q25	Based on your awareness on tillage scheduling service, is it better, the same, or worse than other methods of tillage scheduling?						
	Much Worse <input type="checkbox"/>		Worse <input type="checkbox"/>		About the same <input type="checkbox"/>		Better <input type="checkbox"/>
Q26	Based on your experience with tillage scheduling service, which of the following are you most likely to do for the next season?						
	Return to how I was tilling before <input type="checkbox"/>		Explore available tillage support options on the market <input type="checkbox"/>		Purchase APOLLO tillage scheduling service <input type="checkbox"/>		
Q27	Based on your experience with tillage scheduling service, would you recommend this service to a friend?						
	Definitely will not <input type="checkbox"/>		Probably will not <input type="checkbox"/>		Might or might not <input type="checkbox"/>		Probably will <input type="checkbox"/>
Irrigation Scheduling Service							
Q28	Did the Irrigation Scheduling Service help your farmers/clients to better organize your irrigation operations?						
	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>			No <input type="checkbox"/>			
Q29	Was the irrigation operation using APOLLO advice more effective than the reference one?						
	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>			No <input type="checkbox"/>			
Q30	Do you find irrigation scheduling service useful?						
	Not Useful <input type="checkbox"/>		Useful <input type="checkbox"/>			Very Useful <input type="checkbox"/>	
Q31	Was the irrigation operation using APOLLO advice more effective than how you advice for irrigation without APOLLO?						
	Yes			No			

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	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Q32	Did the Irrigation Scheduling Service help your farmers/clients to decrease your water consumption on irrigation operations?	
	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>	No <input type="checkbox"/>
Q33	Are you satisfied with the way APOLLO irrigation scheduling service performed?	
	Unsatisfied <input type="checkbox"/>	Somewhat Unsatisfied <input type="checkbox"/>
	Neither Satisfied nor Satisfied <input type="checkbox"/>	Somewhat Satisfied <input type="checkbox"/>
	Satisfied <input type="checkbox"/>	
Q34	Considering the overall value of the irrigation scheduling service, was it...	
	A poor value <input type="checkbox"/>	A good value <input type="checkbox"/>
		An exceptional value <input type="checkbox"/>
Q35	How often did you typically use the irrigation scheduling service?	
	Once a year <input type="checkbox"/>	Daily <input type="checkbox"/>
	Weekly <input type="checkbox"/>	Once a month <input type="checkbox"/>
	Every 2-3 months <input type="checkbox"/>	2-3 times a year <input type="checkbox"/>
		Do not use <input type="checkbox"/>
Q36	What is your impression on the overall quality of the information provided by the irrigation scheduling service?	
	Miserable <input type="checkbox"/>	Somewhat Satisfactory <input type="checkbox"/>
	Very Satisfactory <input type="checkbox"/>	Delightful <input type="checkbox"/>
Q37	How accurate did you find the information provided by the service?	
	Not accurate <input type="checkbox"/>	Somewhat accurate <input type="checkbox"/>
	Accurate <input type="checkbox"/>	Very Accurate <input type="checkbox"/>
Q38	How easy was it to learn using this APOLLO service?	
	Hard to learn <input type="checkbox"/>	Somewhat Difficult <input type="checkbox"/>
	Not difficult <input type="checkbox"/>	Very Easy <input type="checkbox"/>
Q39	During irrigation, did this service help your farmers/clients to solve their tasks without additional effort?	
	Not practical <input type="checkbox"/>	Somewhat practical <input type="checkbox"/>
	Practical <input type="checkbox"/>	Very practical <input type="checkbox"/>
Q40	Do you feel you are in control when using this service?	
	Unpredictable <input type="checkbox"/>	Somewhat unpredictable <input type="checkbox"/>
	Predictable <input type="checkbox"/>	Very predictable <input type="checkbox"/>
Q41	Is it exciting and motivating to use this service?	
	Dull <input type="checkbox"/>	Somewhat dull <input type="checkbox"/>
	Interesting <input type="checkbox"/>	Very interesting <input type="checkbox"/>
Q42	What is your overall impression of the service?	
	I don't like it <input type="checkbox"/>	I somewhat don't like it <input type="checkbox"/>
	I somewhat like it <input type="checkbox"/>	I like it <input type="checkbox"/>
Q43	Based on your awareness on irrigation scheduling service, is it better, the same, or worse than other methods of irrigation scheduling?	
	Much Worse <input type="checkbox"/>	Worse <input type="checkbox"/>
	About the same <input type="checkbox"/>	Better <input type="checkbox"/>
		Much Better <input type="checkbox"/>
Q44	Based on your experience with irrigation scheduling service, which of the following are you most likely to do for the next season?	
	Return to how I was irrigating before <input type="checkbox"/>	Explore available irrigation support options on the market <input type="checkbox"/>
		Purchase APOLLO irrigation scheduling service <input type="checkbox"/>
Q45	Based on your experience with irrigation scheduling service, would you recommend this service to a friend?	
	Definitely will not <input type="checkbox"/>	Probably will not <input type="checkbox"/>
	Might or might not <input type="checkbox"/>	Probably will <input type="checkbox"/>
		Definitely will <input type="checkbox"/>
Crop Growth Monitoring Service		
Q46	Did the Crop Growth Monitoring Service help you to better organize your crop growth monitoring operations?	
	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>	No <input type="checkbox"/>
Q47	Was the crop growth monitoring operation using APOLLO advice more effective than the reference one?	
	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>	No <input type="checkbox"/>
Q48	Do you find crop growth monitoring service useful?	
	Not Useful <input type="checkbox"/>	Useful <input type="checkbox"/>
		Very Useful <input type="checkbox"/>

Q49	Was the crop growth monitoring operation using APOLLO advice more effective than how you monitor your crops without APOLLO?						
	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>				No <input type="checkbox"/>		
Q50	Did the crop growth monitoring service help you to decrease your time on crop growth monitoring operations?						
	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>				No <input type="checkbox"/>		
Q51	Are you satisfied with the way APOLLO crop growth monitoring service performed?						
	Unsatisfied <input type="checkbox"/>	Somewhat Unsatisfied <input type="checkbox"/>	Neither Satisfied nor Satisfied <input type="checkbox"/>	Somewhat Satisfied <input type="checkbox"/>	Satisfied <input type="checkbox"/>		
Q52	Considering the overall value of the crop growth monitoring service, was it...						
	A poor value <input type="checkbox"/>		A good value <input type="checkbox"/>			An exceptional value <input type="checkbox"/>	
Q53	How often did you typically use the crop growth monitoring service?						
	Once a year <input type="checkbox"/>	Daily <input type="checkbox"/>	Weekly <input type="checkbox"/>	Once a month <input type="checkbox"/>	Every 2-3 months <input type="checkbox"/>	2-3 times a year <input type="checkbox"/>	Do not use <input type="checkbox"/>
Q54	What is your impression on the overall quality of the information provided by the crop growth monitoring service?						
	Miserable <input type="checkbox"/>	Somewhat Satisfactory <input type="checkbox"/>		Very Satisfactory <input type="checkbox"/>		Delightful <input type="checkbox"/>	
Q55	How accurate did you find the information provided by the service?						
	Not accurate <input type="checkbox"/>	Somewhat accurate <input type="checkbox"/>		Accurate <input type="checkbox"/>		Very Accurate <input type="checkbox"/>	
Q56	How easy was it to learn using this APOLLO service?						
	Hard to learn <input type="checkbox"/>	Somewhat Difficult <input type="checkbox"/>		Not difficult <input type="checkbox"/>		Very Easy <input type="checkbox"/>	
Q57	During crop growth monitoring, did this service help you solve your tasks without additional effort?						
	Not practical <input type="checkbox"/>	Somewhat practical <input type="checkbox"/>		Practical <input type="checkbox"/>		Very practical <input type="checkbox"/>	
Q58	Do you feel you are in control when using this service?						
	Unpredictable <input type="checkbox"/>	Somewhat unpredictable <input type="checkbox"/>		Predictable <input type="checkbox"/>		Very predictable <input type="checkbox"/>	
Q59	Is it exciting and motivating to use this service?						
	Dull <input type="checkbox"/>	Somewhat dull <input type="checkbox"/>		Interesting <input type="checkbox"/>		Very interesting <input type="checkbox"/>	
Q60	What is your overall impression of the service?						
	I don't like it <input type="checkbox"/>	I somewhat don't like it <input type="checkbox"/>		I somewhat like it <input type="checkbox"/>		I like it <input type="checkbox"/>	
Q61	Based on your awareness on crop growth monitoring service, is it better, the same, or worse than other methods of crop growth monitoring?						
	Much Worse <input type="checkbox"/>	Worse <input type="checkbox"/>	About the same <input type="checkbox"/>	Better <input type="checkbox"/>	Much Better <input type="checkbox"/>		
Q62	Based on your experience with crop growth monitoring service, which of the following are you most likely to do for the next season?						
	Return to how I was crop scouting before <input type="checkbox"/>		Explore available crop growth monitoring support options on the market <input type="checkbox"/>			Purchase APOLLO crop growth monitoring service <input type="checkbox"/>	
Q63	Based on your experience with crop growth monitoring service, would you recommend this service to a friend?						
	Definitely will not <input type="checkbox"/>	Probably will not <input type="checkbox"/>	Might or might not <input type="checkbox"/>	Probably will <input type="checkbox"/>	Definitely will <input type="checkbox"/>		
Crop Yield Estimation Service							
Q64	Did the Crop Yield Estimation Service help you to better organize your farmers' /clients' crop harvesting operations?						
	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>				No <input type="checkbox"/>		
Q65	Was the crop harvesting operation using APOLLO advice more effective than the reference one?						
	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>				No <input type="checkbox"/>		
Q66	Do you find crop yield estimation service useful?						

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	Not Useful <input type="checkbox"/>	Useful <input type="checkbox"/>	Very Useful <input type="checkbox"/>	
Q67	Was the crop yield estimation operation using APOLLO advice more effective than how you estimate your crop yields without APOLLO?			
	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>		No <input type="checkbox"/>	
Q68	Did the crop yield estimation service help you to decrease your time on crop yield estimation operations?			
	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>		No <input type="checkbox"/>	
Q69	Are you satisfied with the way APOLLO crop yield estimation service performed?			
	Unsatisfied <input type="checkbox"/>	Somewhat Unsatisfied <input type="checkbox"/>	Neither Satisfied nor Satisfied <input type="checkbox"/>	Somewhat Satisfied <input type="checkbox"/>
Q70	Considering the overall value of the crop yield estimation service, was it...			
	A poor value <input type="checkbox"/>	A good value <input type="checkbox"/>		An exceptional value <input type="checkbox"/>
Q71	How often did you typically use the crop yield estimation service?			
	Once <input type="checkbox"/>	Once a week at the end of the season <input type="checkbox"/>	More than once in week at the end of the season <input type="checkbox"/>	Once a month at the end of the season <input type="checkbox"/>
Q72	What is your impression on the overall quality of the information provided by the crop yield estimation service?			
	Miserable <input type="checkbox"/>	Somewhat Satisfactory <input type="checkbox"/>	Very Satisfactory <input type="checkbox"/>	Delightful <input type="checkbox"/>
Q73	How accurate did you find the information provided by the service?			
	Not accurate <input type="checkbox"/>	Somewhat accurate <input type="checkbox"/>	Accurate <input type="checkbox"/>	Very Accurate <input type="checkbox"/>
Q74	How easy was it to learn using this APOLLO service?			
	Hard to learn <input type="checkbox"/>	Somewhat Difficult <input type="checkbox"/>	Not difficult <input type="checkbox"/>	Very Easy <input type="checkbox"/>
Q75	During crop yield estimation, did this service help you solve your tasks without additional effort?			
	Not practical <input type="checkbox"/>	Somewhat practical <input type="checkbox"/>	Practical <input type="checkbox"/>	Very practical <input type="checkbox"/>
Q76	Do you feel you are in control when using this service?			
	Unpredictable <input type="checkbox"/>	Somewhat unpredictable <input type="checkbox"/>	Predictable <input type="checkbox"/>	Very predictable <input type="checkbox"/>
Q77	Is it exciting and motivating to use this service?			
	Dull <input type="checkbox"/>	Somewhat dull <input type="checkbox"/>	Interesting <input type="checkbox"/>	Very interesting <input type="checkbox"/>
Q78	What is your overall impression of the service?			
	I don't like it <input type="checkbox"/>	I somewhat don't like it <input type="checkbox"/>	I somewhat like it <input type="checkbox"/>	I like it <input type="checkbox"/>
Q79	Based on your awareness on crop yield estimation service, is it better, the same, or worse than other methods of crop yield estimation?			
	Much Worse <input type="checkbox"/>	Worse <input type="checkbox"/>	About the same <input type="checkbox"/>	Better <input type="checkbox"/>
Q80	Based on your experience with crop yield estimation service, which of the following are you most likely to do for the next season?			
	Return to how I was estimating yield before <input type="checkbox"/>	Explore available crop yield estimation support options on the market <input type="checkbox"/>		Purchase APOLLO crop yield estimation service <input type="checkbox"/>
Q81	Based on your experience with crop yield estimation service, would you recommend this service to a friend?			
	Definitely will not <input type="checkbox"/>	Probably will not <input type="checkbox"/>	Might or might not <input type="checkbox"/>	Probably will <input type="checkbox"/>
APOLLO Platform				
Q82	Are you satisfied with the way APOLLO platform performed?			
	Unsatisfied <input type="checkbox"/>	Somewhat Unsatisfied <input type="checkbox"/>	Neither Satisfied nor Satisfied <input type="checkbox"/>	Somewhat Satisfied <input type="checkbox"/>
Q83	Considering the overall value of the APOLLO platform, was it...			

	A poor value <input type="checkbox"/>	A good value <input type="checkbox"/>	An exceptional value <input type="checkbox"/>	
Q84	How did APOLLO platform perform regarding overall quality?			
	Miserably <input type="checkbox"/>	Somewhat Satisfactory <input type="checkbox"/>	Very Satisfactory <input type="checkbox"/>	Delightfully <input type="checkbox"/>
Q85	How easy was to learn using APOLLO platform?			
	Hard to learn <input type="checkbox"/>	Somewhat Difficult <input type="checkbox"/>	Not difficult <input type="checkbox"/>	Very Easy <input type="checkbox"/>
Q86	How did APOLLO platform perform regarding usage experience?			
	Miserably <input type="checkbox"/>	Somewhat Satisfactory <input type="checkbox"/>	Very Satisfactory <input type="checkbox"/>	Delightfully <input type="checkbox"/>
Q87	Based on your awareness on APOLLO platform, is it better, the same, or worse than other methods and platforms?			
	Much Worse <input type="checkbox"/>	Worse <input type="checkbox"/>	About the same <input type="checkbox"/>	Better <input type="checkbox"/>
Q88	Based on your experience with APOLLO platform, how likely are you to be a customer of APOLLO platform (if the price is reasonable)?			
	Definitely will not <input type="checkbox"/>	Probably will not <input type="checkbox"/>	Might or might not <input type="checkbox"/>	Probably will <input type="checkbox"/>
Q89	Based on your experience with APOLLO platform, would you recommend this platform to a friend?			
	Definitely will not <input type="checkbox"/>	Probably will not <input type="checkbox"/>	Might or might not <input type="checkbox"/>	Probably will <input type="checkbox"/>
Q90	Did you experience any difficulties in using APOLLO platform?			
	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>		No <input type="checkbox"/>	

END OF DOCUMENT

